

Survey for Selfdestruct Function of Smart Contracts

* Required

1. Are you a professional smart contract developer? *

yes

no

2. Are you involved in open source software development efforts? *

Yes

No

3. Please describe your main role in developing smart contracts? *

Testing

Development

Management

Other: _____

4. How many years of experience do you have in Ethereum smart contract development/testing/project management(decimals ok)? *

Your answer _____

5. What is your current country of residence? *

Your answer _____

Read Me: The only way to remove code from the blockchain is when a contract at that address performs the selfdestruct operation. In the following part, we will ask some questions about Selfdestruct function

6. Will you add Selfdestruct functions in your future smart contracts?

Yes (Go to Q7)

No (Go to Q8)

7. Why do you add Selfdestruct functions

Your answer

8. Why do you not add Selfdestruct functions

Your answer

As an appreciation of your time and valuable inputs, we will give out 50 USD Amazon vouchers to two randomly selected participants. If you want to enter the raffle, please kindly enter your email. (Optional)

Your answer

Submit